

PWANI UNIVERSITY

EAP B403 ECONOMICS OF EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL PLANNING

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MINISTRY OF EDUCATION

ST. THOMAS GIRLS HIGH SCHOOL

STRATEGIC PLAN

2023 - 2027

School Motto

Strive for Excellence

Vision

To become a revered institution while grooming the child of today to be a capable, responsible and performing Citizen

Mission

To instill knowledge and skills through effective learning

Core Values

Accountability, Empathy, Equality, Critical thinking and Care for health

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Summary

Strategic planning and implementation is very important in the running of any institution today. Proper planning is a requirement for the success of any education institution, business or any endeavor. This strategic plan is intended to offer a well laid plan that will be used in developing St. Thomas Girls High School into a reputable learning institution within the next 5 years.

St. Thomas Girls has a responsibility to provide quality and relevant education thus contributing to increased research and knowledge thereby brightening the future of the coming generation. We are destined not only to produce disciplined students but also responsible men in the society who will be helpful to the parents and all members of the community. We also offer life skills, home science and computer studies classes.

This strategic plan (2023 - 2027) offers a broad framework for improving education within the school. It focuses on areas that need much concern in order for the institution to discharge its duty of providing quality education and imparting knowledge, skills, values and attitude necessary for nation building. It will also offer well declared procedures to be followed in the implementation of the plan.

On behalf of the School Staff, PTA and members of the non-teaching staff, I welcome all parties to identify areas that they may wish to help to see the success of the plan.

(Sign)

Lydia Burale (Mrs)

PRINCIPAL

1.0 HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

St. Thomas girls high school started in 1963 as a missionary school under the leadership of the Catholic church. The then headmaster was Mr. Kazungu. The school started as a mixed day school with a population of about 60 students in form one and form two. Through the help of Mr. Kazungu and the then deputy Dr. Robert Aran, who is currently a lecturer at the University of Nairobi, the school enrolled over 80 students in 1964 in form one.

The first form one class of 1963 sat for their first junior exam in 1964. In the same year, the missionaries and the community under the leadership of the then chief Mghale organized a big fundraising that facilitated the construction of a library and 4 classrooms and a staff room. Books were brought with the extra money and needy students fee cleared which enabled needy students to finish their education.

The first B.O.M. chairman was Mr. Samwel wanjala. The management with the help of the missionaries led by Mr. Britney sourced funds to build the school fence and a dining hall for the students to have their meals in school. They also managed to establish a laboratory by sourcing funds from Volunteers. The school was later changed to a girls school in 1995 under the leadership of Mrs Annabel and was given full boarding in 2010.

Since the start of the school, the following personnel have served as as school principals:

- | | |
|------------------------|--------------|
| 1. Mr. John Kazungu | 1963 - 1967 |
| 2. Mr. Robert Bobs | 1968 - 1978 |
| 3. Mr. Philip Otuya | 1979 - 1981 |
| 4. Mr. Kigen Mghalo | 1982 - 1994 |
| 5. Mrs. Annabel Akello | 1995 - 2008 |
| 6. Mrs. Cate Maya | 2009 - 2015 |
| 7. Mrs. Lydiah Burale | 2016 to date |

Sponsorship

The school is sponsored by The Catholic Church of East Africa. The land on which the school stands was donated by the community.

Geographical Location

The school is located in Kilifi town, a few kilometers from the county offices of Kilifi County.

2.0 CONTEXTUAL ANALYSIS

St. Thomas Girls High School was registered as a mixed day school in 1963. Currently the school is a boarding Girls school with 4 streams and with an enrolment of over 900 students.

(a) School data

Year	Number of Students
2022	916
2021	845
2020	751
2019	784
2018	643

(b) CBE

Approved CBE	25
TSC	20
BOM	16

(c) Books Ratio

Main Course Books	Ratio
English	1:1
Kiswahili	1:1
Chemistry	1:1
Physics	1:1
Biology	1:1
Business Studies	1:2
Agriculture	1:1
History	1:2
Geography	1:1
CRE	1:1

(d) Toilets

Students	Teachers	Non - teaching Staff
Tuition and Dormitory Area	Administration Area	Administration Area next to Teacher's Toilets
1:39	1:6	1:3

(e) Transition rate for all classes for the 5 years completion and progression. Number of dropouts per year

Year	Left	New Admission	Variance	Total
2017	20	20	0	601
2018	23	36	13	643
2019	26	21	5	784
2020	30	18	12	751
2021	21	42	21	845
2022	29	31	2	916

(f) KCSE Results 2019 - 2021

Grade	A	A-	B+	B	B-	C+	C	C-	D+	D	D-	E	ENTRY	M.S	M.G	IMP'NT
Year 2021	2	4	17	23	24	35	20	15	10	3			153	7.359	C+	0.391
Year 2020	1	8	28	30	32	20	18	11	9	6			163	7.748	C+	0.163
Year 2019		10	15	20	24	30	22	16	5	1			143	7.585	C+	0.532

Economic and Social Aspect in the Catchment Area

The main economic activity in the school is dairy farming and fish farming. The major cultural highlight in the school is that they conduct initiation rites to adulthood every November. Hot climate in the region is a challenge in the catchment area therefore impacting negatively on the school.

Management of the School

The school is under the management of BOM which oversees the management of the resources, employs and disciplines teachers and non teaching staff. The head of the school is the principal who is assisted by two deputy principals and the various HOD's. The deputies are in charge of discipline and internal affairs. They also have the mandate to chair board meetings and staff room meetings in the absence of the principal.

The various departments in the school include; Languages, Sciences, Mathematics, Technical, Games and sports, Guidance and Counseling, Clubs and Societies, Boarding and Dean of students. The Student body is headed by the student's council. The chairman of the student council is the school Captain assisted by two deputies. The support staff is under the leadership of the school secretary who supervises the work.

PTA comprises the parent representative per class and two teachers who represent the teaching staff. Parents provide support to the school through fee payment and donations especially during the harvest season.

Functions of the School

The school offers the 8-4-4 curriculum comprising of 13 subjects i.e.

1. Mathematics
2. English
3. Kiswahili
4. Biology
5. Chemistry
6. Physics
7. History
8. CRE
9. Business Studies
10. Agriculture
11. Geography
12. French
13. Computer Studies

The school also offers Music and aviation classes during weekends to interested students. Games and sports are also practiced within the school.

Games

1. Netball
2. Football
3. Volleyball
4. Handball
5. Rugby
6. Table Tennis
7. Hokey

8. Badminton and
9. Computer games

Other Activities

- Community outreach programmes
- Drama
- Clubs and Societies

Clubs include

1. Peace club
2. Red Cross club
3. Wildlife Club
4. Integrity Club
5. Volleyball Club
6. Maths Club
7. Scouting Club

Resources Adequacy

The school stands on 25 acres of land. The facilities in the school include; The staff room, 12 classrooms, three laboratories, School Hall, 8 Dormitories, Dining hall, Computer Laboratory, Generator house, Teachers quarters, School farm and workshop buildings. On the farm section, there are Drought resistant maize and Sukuma wiki. There is also an irrigated yam plantation and a greenhouse where Tomatoes are planted. Watermelons are also planted in the farm.

The school has a standby generator in case of power shortage. It has piped water and also storage tanks for keeping rain water. The school also has a 64 seater Isuzu bus as a means of transport. The school gets its funding from the government and from parents in the form of fees.

SWOT Analysis

Schools strengths

1. A qualified and committed staff.
2. Well structured management.
3. Organized school body.
4. Adequate resource materials for teaching and learning.
5. Well equipped laboratories.

6. Technical efficient population.
7. Spacious hall.
8. Modern computers and mobile projectors.

School Weaknesses

1. Inadequate water.
2. Lack of internet for computers.
3. Unavailability of adequate playing field.
4. Extremely hot climatic conditions.
5. Lack of a well organized alumni association denying the school capability of fully tapping the potentialities of the past.

Opportunities

1. Demand for education in the coastal region.
2. Subsidies from the government.
3. Donations from the community.
4. Availability of Modern ICT equipment from the ministry.

Threats

1. Delayed fee payment.
2. Inadequate teachers and support staff.
3. Noise pollution due to close proximity to a highway.
4. Deficit eight teachers in the CBC.
5. Poor economy.
6. High poverty level in the coastal region.
7. Teenage pregnancy.
8. Many students are left under the care of grandparents which compromises student discipline.
9. Cases of use of mobile phones in school.

PESTLE Analysis

Political

1. Services have been brought close to the people through devolution.
2. Good relationship between the school and the county head of education helps the school to tap financial support from the county government.

Economic

1. Increased prices of commodities in the country which has strained school resources.
2. Low income of the parents in the coastal region.

Social Cultural

1. Security has been enhanced because of the good relationship between the community and the school.
2. Being a mission school, the church offers spiritual guidance and psychological support.

Technological

Lack of free internet connectivity in the school poses challenges in the use of advanced technology for research purposes.

Legal

1. Reduced cases of drug use among teenagers due to the banning of the sale of alcohol to those under 18 years.
2. Children rights upheld as stated in the constitution of Kenya.
3. Use of guidance and counselling instead of corporal punishment.

Environmental

1. Extremely hot climatic conditions which result in poor agriculture.
2. Noise pollution from the nearby road.

Key issues

The school needs to address the following major problems;

- Negative attitude of students towards learning.
- Inadequate infrastructure eg. Classrooms.
- Employ more trained CBC teachers.
- Discipline of students due to parental negligence.
- Delays in the implementation of development projects such as the biogas toilet which has not been completed since 2015.
- Reducing school mean due to enrolment of more students.

3.0 STRATEGIC DIRECTION

Vision

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Mission

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Motto

Strive for excellence

Core Values

1. Accountability
2. Empathy
3. Equity
4. Critical thinking
5. Care for health

Strategic Objectives

1. Varying counseling approaches to students.
2. Use e-learning as a new method of learning.
3. Undertake group work.
4. Raise school KCSE mean to 9.5 by 2024.
5. Renovate buildings and complete the construction of the biogas toilet.

By the end of 2023

1. The Biogas toilet shall have been completed.
2. Repainting of the classes and the school hall.
3. Renovation of the staff room with no tiles and proper chairs.

4. Construction of toilets for teachers near the administration block.
5. Additional games kits.
6. Additional water points.
7. Chairs in the classes.
8. Proper fencing.

By the end of 2024

1. Wifi in the computer lab and in the staff room.
2. Modern computers.
3. Bakery.
4. Modern PA system.
5. Additional Chairs.
6. Installing Whiteboards.
7. Installing graph boards.

By the end of 2025

1. Building a modern gate.
2. Renovation of the library.
3. Building new laboratory.

By the end of 2026

1. Installing ferns in the classes.
2. Modern radio station.
3. Digital portable projectors.

From 2027

Building Agricultural research block.

4.0 IMPLEMENTATION

Objective 1: Varying Counseling sessions on the students

Strategy	Activity	Who	Time Frame	Resources	Source of Funding	Assumption	Output/Indicator
Varying counseling Sessions	Group counseling. Open forums.	HOD guidance and counseling. Head teacher. Deputy head teacher. Colleague willing teachers.	2023 - 2027	Books. Magazines. Visual Aids.	Fees. County government. Donors.	Good cooperation of parents in paying fees. Donors will come through to assist.	Improvement in internal and external examination.

Objective 2: Use of e-learning as a new method of learning

Strategy	Activity	Who	Time Frame	Resources	Source of Funding	Assumption	Output/Indicator
Buy and use e-learning materials	Buy Generate Learn E-learning	Computer lab technician Concerned teachers	2023-2027	Computers. Projectors. E-learning	Parents CDF	CDF will disburse money in time Parents will pay fee in	Timetable E-learning materials KCSE

	activities	Head teacher		materials. Headphones.		time	mean score
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Objective 3: Undertake group work

Strategy	Activity	Who	Time frame	Resources	Source of Funding	Assumption	Output/Indicator
Building group discussion tables	Construction Launching	Head teacher BOM Teachers in charge of development	2023 - 2027	Human Construction materials	CDF BOM Parent funding Donor funds	Parents will pay fee in time CDF will disburse funds in time	Improvement in KCSE exams

Objective 4: Raise School KCSE mean to 9.5 by 2024

Strategy	Activity	Who	Time frame	Resources	Source of Funding	Assumption	Output/Indicator
Ensure effective learning and teaching.	Syllabus completion in time. Addition of teachers. Increased evaluation exercises.	Teachers. Students. E-learning materials.	2023 - 2027	Parents Government grants. Donors.	Parents paying school fees. Timely grants. Willingness of donors.		Improved KCSE results. Attendance of debate activities. Syllabus coverage done in time.

	Attending field trips, Symposi ums etc. Avail enough revision materials. Enhance e-learning						Students revise their notes.
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Objective 5: Renovate Buildings, Fence and Complete the Construction of Biogas Toilet

Strategy	Activity	Who	Time Frame	Resources	Source of Funding	Assumption	Output/Indicator
Completion of the Biogas toilet	Buying the building materials	Principal	By the end of 2023	Funds from school	Fee from parents	Parents pay fee	Construction of the biogas toilet
Repair of classes, instilling whiteboard and renovation of school hall	Renovation	Principal	By the end of 2023	Funds from school	Fee from parents	Parents pay fee	Classes and the school hall are renovated
Renovation of staff room and construction of staff toilets	Availing tiles and carrying out renovation	Principal	By the end of 2023	Funds from school	Fee from parents	Parents pay fee	Staffroom is renovated and staff toilets constructed

Renovation of the fence and erection of a modern gate	Purchase of wire mesh and renovation Purchase of posts for fencing	Principal	By the end of 2024	Funds from school	Fee from parents	Parents pay fee	Fence renovated Gate constructed
Renovation of library and laboratories	Purchase of materials	Principal	By the end of 2025	Funds from school	Fee from parents	Parents pay fee	Library and laboratories renovated
Building Agriculture research block	Purchase of construction materials	Principal	By the end of 2027	Funds from school	Fee from parents	Parents pay fee	Agriculture research block constructed

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